

FINAL REPORT

1 General Information

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Project title: Multi-qubit gates for the efficient exploration of Hilbert space with superconducting qubit systems

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2 Summary

Quantum computing has made rapid progress in recent years, with significant improvements in hardware performance across multiple platforms. Superconducting qubits in particular have benefited from longer coherence times and steadily increasing gate fidelities. Despite these advances, major challenges remain before quantum computers can be used reliably at scale. Beyond further improving coherence, it is crucial to develop efficient methods for preparing complex, highly entangled multi-qubit quantum states with high fidelity. Such capabilities are essential for near-term quantum algorithms, especially variational approaches like the Variational Quantum Eigensolver (VQE), as well as for quantum error correction schemes.

Two key strategies can substantially improve quantum state preparation: increasing the connectivity of a quantum processor and extending the available gate set beyond the standard combination of single-qubit gates and a single two-qubit entangling gate. Both approaches can reduce circuit depth, limit error accumulation, and enable more expressive quantum operations. This project has therefore focused on exploring efficient methods to generate multi-qubit states in a superconducting architecture based on transmon qubits combined with tunable couplers.

The research pursued two complementary directions. The first investigated architectures with increased connectivity enabled by a single tunable coupler connecting multiple circuit elements. In a system of three qubits coupled through one tunable element, theoretical analysis and numerical simulations showed that high-fidelity controlled-controlled phase gates could be implemented. Using optimal control techniques, the protocol was first demonstrated on a two-qubit subset, achieving record-high two-qubit gate fidelities above 99.9%. This highlighted the potential of tunable couplers to realize precise and efficient entangling operations. Complementary to this, a second approach based on parametric couplings demonstrated that a central tunable coupler can serve multiple functions within the processor. In addition to mediating entangling gates, the coupler could be used for qubit reset, leakage reduction, and tunable readout. This multifunctionality is particularly attractive for scalable architectures, as it reduces the need for additional control and readout lines, saving critical hardware resources.

The second main research direction focused on efficient entanglement generation in standard grid-like architectures with nearest-neighbour connectivity. Here, perfect state transfer protocols were shown, both theoretically and experimentally, to generate highly entangled Greenberger–Horne–Zeilinger (GHZ) states. Importantly, these protocols can be generalized to create graph states as well as other classes of entanglement, such as W-states. This demonstrates that even architectures with limited connectivity can support

powerful state preparation techniques when combined with appropriate dynamical protocols. In addition we have investigated control schemes and pulses, as well as designs for superconducting quantum circuits that allow us to protect the qubits from the coupling to a dissipative environment.

Overall, the project shows that architectural design and advanced control methods play a central role in overcoming current limitations in quantum state preparation, with direct implications for variational algorithms, quantum simulation, and error correction.

Zusammenfassung

Die Quanteninformationsverarbeitung hat in den vergangenen Jahren erhebliche Fortschritte erzielt, insbesondere durch verbesserte Hardwareleistung auf unterschiedlichen Plattformen. Supraleitende Qubits profitieren dabei von guten Kohärenzzeiten und stetig steigenden Gatter-Fidelitäten. Trotz dieser Entwicklungen bestehen weiterhin fundamentale Herausforderungen, bevor Quantencomputer zuverlässig im großen Maßstab eingesetzt werden können. Neben der Optimierung der Kohärenzeigenschaften ist die effiziente Erzeugung komplexer, stark verschränkter Multi-Qubit-Zustände mit hoher Genauigkeit von zentraler Bedeutung. Solche Fähigkeiten sind essenziell für variationale Algorithmen wie den Variational Quantum Eigensolver (VQE) sowie für die Implementierung von Quantenfehlerkorrekturverfahren.

Zur Verbesserung der Zustandspräparation wurden zwei Ansätze identifiziert: (i) die Erhöhung der Konnektivität innerhalb des Quantenprozessors und (ii) die Erweiterung der Menge an verfügbaren Quantengatter über Ein-Qubit-Gattern und einem Zwei-Qubit-Verschränkungsgatter hinaus. Beide Ansätze tragen zur Reduktion der Schaltungstiefe, zur Minimierung von Fehlerakkumulation und zur Realisierung effizienter Quantenoperationen bei. Das vorliegende Projekt konzentrierte sich auf die Entwicklung effizienter Methoden zur Erzeugung von Multi-Qubit-Zuständen in einer supraleitenden Architektur auf Basis von Transmon-Qubits in Kombination mit abstimmbaren Kopplungselementen.

Es wurden zwei komplementäre Richtungen verfolgt: Erstens wurden Architekturen mit erhöhter Konnektivität untersucht, die durch ein einzelnes abstimmbares Kopplungselement mehrere Schaltungskomponenten verbinden. In einem System aus drei Qubits, gekoppelt über ein solches Element, zeigten theoretische Analysen und numerische Simulationen die Realisierbarkeit hochpräziser kontrollierter Phasengatter (CCPhase). Mithilfe optimaler Steuerungstechniken konnte das Protokoll zunächst an einem Zwei-Qubit-Subset demonstriert werden, wobei Gate-Fidelitäten von über 99,9 % erreicht wurden. Ergänzend wurde gezeigt, dass ein zentraler abstimmbarer Koppler multifunktional eingesetzt werden kann, etwa zur Durchführung von 2-Qubit

Gatter, zum Qubit-Reset, zur Leckagereduktion und zur kontrollierbaren Auslese. Diese Multifunktionalität reduziert den Bedarf an zusätzlichen Steuer- und Ausleseleitungen und ist daher besonders attraktiv für skalierbare Architekturen.

Zweitens wurde die effiziente Erzeugung von Verschränkung in gitterartigen Architekturen mit paarweiser Qubit-Qubit Konnektivität untersucht. Hierbei konnten Protokolle für perfekten Zustandstransfer sowohl theoretisch als auch experimentell zur Erzeugung hochgradig verschränkter Greenberger–Horne–Zeilinger (GHZ)-Zustände validiert werden. Diese Protokolle lassen sich verallgemeinern, um Graphzustände sowie andere Klassen von Verschränkungen, wie W-Zustände, zu erzeugen. Darüber hinaus wurden Steuerungsschemata und Kontrollpulse, sowie neuartige Qubitdesigns entwickelt, die eine verbesserte Isolation der Qubits gegenüber dissipativen Umgebungen ermöglichen.

Insgesamt zeigt das Projekt die zentrale Rolle von Architekturdesign und fortgeschrittenen Steuerungsmethoden bei der Überwindung aktueller Limitierungen in der Zustandspräparation auf. Die Ergebnisse haben unmittelbare Relevanz für variationale Algorithmen, Quantensimulationen und die Implementierung von Fehlerkorrekturverfahren.

3 Progress Report

The background of this project is rooted in the observation that state preparation efficiency in quantum processors can be significantly enhanced by architectural choices and control strategies. In particular, increasing qubit connectivity and extending the available gate set beyond standard single- and two-qubit operations can reduce circuit depth and accumulated errors. Superconducting architectures based on fixed-frequency transmon qubits combined with tunable couplers offer an attractive platform to explore these ideas, as they combine good coherence properties with flexible, dynamically controllable interactions.

The main objective of the project was to develop and demonstrate efficient methods for generating entangled multi-qubit states in such architectures. This included exploring **enhanced connectivity using multi-element tunable couplers (Result 1)**, as well as identifying **dynamical protocols that enable efficient entanglement generation** even in architectures with only nearest-neighbour coupling (**Result 2**). With the control capabilities that were developed in these projects we furthermore showed how to design **robust pulses** that are less sensitive to parameter fluctuations, such as drive amplitude drifts, than standard gates. We also investigated **novel control schemes** based on multi-photon processes, and **designed a superconducting quantum circuit** in which the qubit mode is decoupled from its environment (**Result 3**).

Result 1: N-way couplers for enhanced connectivity

In the work by Gerhard Huber et al. [Huber2025], we introduce a **parametric multi-element coupling architecture** that enables flexible coherent and dissipative control of superconducting qubits (see Figure 1). We show that by parametrically modulating a shared tunable coupler, we can dynamically generate effective interactions between qubits while preserving the advantages of fixed-frequency transmon designs. We demonstrate that a single coupling element can serve multiple essential functions within a quantum processor. Specifically, we show how the coupler can mediate high-fidelity entangling gates, implement fast qubit reset, reduce leakage into non-computational states, and enable tunable qubit readout. We achieve these functionalities by selecting appropriate modulation frequencies and amplitudes, which allows us to selectively activate coherent or dissipative processes. Our results highlight that parametric couplers are not merely interaction mediators but versatile resources for quantum control and that consolidating multiple control and measurement tasks into a single coupling element significantly reduces hardware overhead, making this architecture particularly attractive for scalable superconducting quantum computing.

Figure 1. Microscope image of the chip used in [Huber2025]. The qubits (blue), coupler (green), and resonator (yellow) are highlighted. Single-qubit drives are applied through the feedline. Qubit measurements are performed using dispersively coupled resonators connected to feedlines, unless stated otherwise.

To make use of the enhanced connectivity in this architecture we investigate the **direct implementation of controlled-controlled-phase (CC-Phase) gates** using a **tunable coupler shared between three qubits** in the manuscript by N. Glaser et al [Glaser2023]. We address the challenge that three-qubit gates are typically realized through long sequences of two-qubit operations, which increases circuit depth and error rates. With the architecture containing three fixed-frequency transmon qubits coupled via a single tunable coupling element we can engineer effective multi-qubit interactions without tuning the qubit frequencies. We show that by dynamically controlling the tunable coupler, we can induce strong conditional phase interactions among the three qubits. Using optimal control techniques, we design control pulses that suppress leakage and unwanted transitions while maximizing gate fidelity. Through detailed numerical simulations, we demonstrate that CCPhase gates with high fidelity (above 99.9%) can be achieved under realistic experimental conditions.

To demonstrate the experimental feasibility of this concept we develop a **sensitivity-adapted closed-loop optimization framework** to realize a short, high-fidelity **controlled-Z (CZ) gate**. To reduce population leakage during required adiabatic passages through avoided level crossings when tuning the coupling element, we employ a sensitivity-adaptive closed-loop optimization method to design complex pulse shapes. We compare the performance of Gaussian-square, Fourier-series, and piecewise-constant-slope (PiCoS) pulse parametrizations and are able to reach 99.9% controlled-Z gate fidelity using a 64ns long Fourier-series pulse defined by only seven parameters (see experimental results shown Figure 2). These high-fidelity values are achieved by analyzing the optimized pulse shapes to identify and systematically mitigate signal-line distortions

in the experiment using pre-compensation filters. To improve the convergence speed of the optimization we implement an adaptive cost function, which continuously maximizes the sensitivity. The demonstrated method provides also the basis for tune-up and recalibration of superconducting quantum processors.

Figure 2. Optimized pulse-shape parametrizations and interleaved randomized benchmarking results comparing (a, c) the Fourier-series parametrization and (b, d) the PiCoS parametrization, with gate errors denoted as ϵ . Panels (a) and (b) display the results before applying pulse pre-compensation, while panels (c) and (d) show the results after the implementation of pre-compensation.

Result 2: Efficient state preparation with controllable simultaneous couplings

In a more standard quantum processor architecture qubits are only pairwise coupled to each other. An important question is then, how quantum states and entanglement can be generated efficiently in such an architecture. Within this project we have, therefore, investigated parity-dependent state transfer as a mechanism for directly generating entanglement in chains of superconducting qubits. We have first developed a theoretical framework for realizing effective non-local, parity-dependent interactions in chains of superconducting qubits [Naegele2022]. We show that although the physical couplings are strictly local, carefully engineered dynamics can give rise to effective interactions that depend on the global parity of the system. This allows us to mediate non-local correlations without introducing additional coupling elements.

We then show that by engineering the coupling strengths within a qubit chain, we can realize a state transfer protocol whose dynamics depend explicitly on the parity of the excitation subspace also in experiment in the work by F. Roy [Roy2025]. Starting from simple initial states, we show that coherent evolution under the engineered Hamiltonian produces entanglement in a single dynamical step and that the parity dependence leads naturally to the generation of highly entangled Greenberger–Horne–Zeilinger (GHZ) states, without the need for individual multi-qubit gates (see Figure 3). With that we realize an efficient and scalable method for entanglement generation in superconducting qubit chains, which offers a powerful

alternative to gate-based entanglement schemes, well suited for near-term quantum processors with limited connectivity.

Figure 3. Reconstructed density matrix of the experimentally realised GHZ state (solid bars), with ideal values plotted as black wire-frames. Allowing for an arbitrary Z rotation of the final state yields a state preparation fidelity of a GHZ-state of 88.08%. The inset shows the circuit diagram for the GHZ state creation on a 3-qubit chain with the parity-dependent 3-qubit gate after the Hadamard gates H.

As an extension we currently explore a new class of time-independent Hamiltonians defined on a lattice, which are capable of **preparing W states, another class of entangled states, thereby expanding the set of fully-entangled states** achievable with this strategy (J. Romero et al, in preparation). Current experiments have been realized on a chain of three fixed-frequency transmons, as shown in Figure 4. By fine-tuning the simultaneous parametric drives applied to the two couplers, we recover the dynamics seen in Figure 4b. This effectively maps an excitation prepared in the central qubit into a uniform superposition, thus generating a W-state in a single operation lasting only 160ns. Tomographic data taken over 7.5 hours yields an average state fidelity of 98% as presented in Figure 4c. Efforts to scale up to larger experimental systems are currently in progress. Most notably, our protocol achieves linear time-scaling for 1D chains and is promoted to sub-linear times for 2D lattices.

Figure 4. W -state preparation with simultaneous time-independent control in a three-qubit chain. (a) Circuit diagram of the relevant elements. The system is controlled by simultaneous parametric drives (red) to the two tunable couplers (gray). (b) Population dynamics of all three qubits, showing experimental data (dots) and fit with decay (continuous lines). Dashed vertical lines represent multiples of the synthesis time of 160ns. At odd multiples, the excitation is equally spread along the chain. (c) Density matrix recovered from tomographic data (solid bars), compared to ideal W state (dashed wireframes). Inset in the upper-right color shows the full synthesis circuit.

Result 3: Qubit control schemes

The expertise gained in this project on optimal control was also utilized to **investigate robust pulse schemes**. In the work by Emily Wrigth et al. [Wright2025], we investigate how to design superconducting qubit gates that remain high-fidelity in the presence of parameter fluctuations and experimental uncertainty.

We address the practical challenge that qubit frequencies, coupling strengths, and control amplitudes inevitably drift over time, limiting gate performance and increasing calibration overhead. We develop control strategies that incorporate parameter variations directly into the gate optimization process. We show that by shaping control pulses to minimize sensitivity to fluctuations, we can significantly enhance gate robustness without sacrificing fidelity. Specifically we design control pulses that are robust against frequency fluctuations (FROG) and pulses that are less sensitive to amplitude fluctuations (AROG). Using numerical simulations, we demonstrate that the resulting gates maintain strong performance across a broad range of realistic parameter deviations. We further analyze the trade-off between maximum achievable fidelity and robustness, showing that slightly reducing peak fidelity can lead to substantially improved stability under noise and drift, as shown in Figure 5. These robust pulses suppress errors e.g. from drive amplitude drifts over 15 times more than a Gaussian pulse with derivative removal by adiabatic gate (DRAG) corrections. Our results demonstrate that robustness-optimized gates outperform conventionally optimized gates in realistic experimental conditions.

Figure 5. Gate errors for different types of gates extracted from randomized benchmarking (RB) experiments for 10 hours each day for 11 days. A standard DRAG gate is compared to a frequency robust gate (FROG) and a gate that is robust against amplitude errors (AROG). RB curves for (b) day 6 and (c) day 10 are connected by lines to time points of interest in (a). The error bars at each sequence length N_c reflect the standard deviation across different randomizations, and the insets show the mean standard deviation over all sequence lengths.

In another work by J. Schirk et al. [Schirk2025], we investigate **subharmonic control techniques for manipulating a fluxonium qubit** using a filtered flux line that provides Purcell-protection to the qubit as shown in Figure 6. We address the challenge that strongly coupled control drives can introduce unwanted decoherence and enhanced relaxation through the control circuitry. We show that by driving the qubit at subharmonic frequencies of its transition, we can achieve coherent control while significantly suppressing radiative decay. We demonstrate theoretically and experimentally that subharmonic driving enables high-fidelity qubit operations without requiring direct resonant excitation. By coupling the fluxonium qubit to a carefully engineered flux line, we show that control-induced losses are minimized. We analyze the resulting dynamics and confirm that multi-photon transitions dominate the control process.

These sub-harmonic processes have been investigated further by L. Huang et al. [Huang2025]. In this work we, together with the group of Prof. Peter Rabl (WMI), develop a **theoretical framework to describe multi-photon processes in driven quantum systems** and explore their applications in quantum control. We show that multi-photon transitions provide access to otherwise forbidden or weakly accessible transitions, enabling new control strategies beyond standard single-photon driving. Together with the experimental results this shows that subharmonic control provides a powerful and flexible method for manipulating fluxonium qubits while preserving their excellent coherence properties. This approach is

particularly well suited for advanced superconducting qubit architectures where strong driving and low dissipation must be simultaneously achieved.

Figure 6. (a) The setup at the low-temperature stages of the cryostat, including the readout resonator and two switchable flux-line configurations [unfiltered (UF) and low-pass filtered (LP)]. An additional microwave (MW) line is added for comparison and benchmarking. (b) A false-color micrograph of the fluxonium (blue) with a galvanically coupled flux line (red) and a capacitively coupled readout resonator (yellow). The additional MW line is located outside of the micrograph cut-out shown here. (c) A sketch of the power spectral density $S(\omega)$ for the resonant (blue) and subharmonic drive (red) setups. The shaded area indicates the pass band of the low-pass filter. (d) Integrated histograms for the T_1 (solid), T_2^* (dashed), and T_2^e (dotted) for unfiltered (blue) and filtered (red) flux-line configurations. The vertical lines with shaded areas illustrate the median and standard deviation.

From our work on multi-qubit couplings it became obvious that unwanted couplings leading to cross-talk significantly limits the practicability of quantum processors. In the work by F. Pfeiffer et al. [Pfeiffer2024] we therefore study an **alternative qubit design (the P-mon) for efficiently decoupling a non-linear qubit mode from its environment** to suppress decoherence and improve coherence times. With that we address the challenge that coupling to control and readout circuitry introduces necessarily unwanted dissipation, particularly in highly anharmonic superconducting qubits. We make use of the design flexibility of superconducting quantum circuits to form a multimode element—an artificial molecule—with symmetry-protected modes. The proposed circuit consists of three superconducting islands

coupled to a central island via Josephson junctions. It exhibits two essential nonlinear modes, one of which is flux insensitive and used as the protected qubit mode. The second mode is flux tunable and serves via a cross-Kerr-type coupling as a mediator to control the dispersive coupling of the qubit mode to the readout resonator. We demonstrate the Purcell protection of the qubit mode by measuring relaxation times that are independent of the mediated dispersive coupling. We show that the coherence of the qubit is not limited by photon-induced dephasing when detuning the mediator mode from the readout resonator and thereby reducing the dispersive coupling. The resulting highly protected ‘P-mon’ qubit with tunable interactions may serve as a basic building block of a scalable quantum processor architecture, in which qubit decoherence is strongly suppressed.

Figure 7. False-color microscope image of the P-mon qubit sample including the coupler to the readout resonator (left) and the flux line (top) with the four islands labeled 0, 1, 2 and 3. The close-up shows the Josephson junctions and SQUID connected to the central island 0.

4 Published Project Results

4.1 Category A – Articles in peer-reviewed journals, contributions to peer-reviewed conferences or to anthology volumes, and book publications

(Authors supported directly by the project and the PI are highlighted in bold face)

[Glaser2023] *Controlled-controlled-phase gates for superconducting qubits mediated by a shared tunable coupler.*

N. J. Glaser, F. Roy and **S. Filipp**.

Phys. Rev. Appl. 19, 044001 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevApplied.19.044001>

[Glaser2025] *Closed-loop optimization for high-fidelity controlled-Z gates in superconducting qubits.*

N. J. Glaser, F. A. Roy, **I. Tsitsilin**, L. Koch, N. Bruckmoser, J. Schirk, J. H. Romeiro, G. B.P. Huber, F. Wallner, M. Singh, G. Krylov, A. Marx, L. Södergren, C. M. F. Schneider, M. Werninghaus, **S. Filipp**.

Phys. Rev. Applied 24, 024048 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1103/pckq-2cs>

[Huber2025] *Parametric multi-element coupling architecture for coherent and dissipative control of superconducting qubits.*

G. B. P. Huber, F. A. Roy, L. Koch, **I. Tsitsilin**, J. Schirk, N. J. Glaser, N. Bruckmoser, C. Schweizer, J. Romeiro, G. Krylov, M. Singh, F. X. Haslbeck, M. Knudsen, A. Marx, F. Pfeiffer, C. Schneider, F. Wallner, D. Bunch, L. Richard, L. Södergren, K. Liegener, M. Werninghaus, **S. Filipp**.

Phys. Rev. X Quantum 6, 030313 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1103/9shv-l4cx>

[Naegele2022] *Effective non-local parity-dependent couplings in qubit chains.*

M. Nägele, C. Schweizer, F. Roy, and **S. Filipp**.

Phys. Rev. Research 4, 033166 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevResearch.4.033166>

[Pfeiffer2024] *Efficient decoupling of a non-linear qubit mode from its environment.*

F. Pfeiffer, M. Werninghaus, C. Schweizer, N. Bruckmoser, L. Koch, N. J. Glaser, G. Huber, D. Bunch, F. X. Haslbeck, M. Knudsen, **G. Krylov**, K. Liegener, A. Marx, L. Richard, J. H. Romeiro, F. Roy, J. Schirk, C. Schneider, M. Singh, L. Södergren, **I. Tsitsilin**, F. Wallner, C. A. Riofrío, **S. Filipp**.

Phys. Rev. X 14, 041007 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevX.14.041007>

[Roy2025] *Parity-dependent state transfer for direct entanglement generation.*

F. A. Roy, J. H. Romeiro, L. Koch, **I. Tsitsilin**, J. Schirk, N. J. Glaser, N. Bruckmoser, M. Singh, F. X. Haslbeck, G. B. P. Huber, G. Krylov, A. Marx, F. Pfeiffer, C. M. F. Schneider, C. Schweizer, F. Wallner, D. Bunch, L. Richard, L. Södergren, K. Liegener, M. Werninghaus, **S. Filipp**.

Nat. Commun. 16, 2660 (2025) <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-025-57818-2>

[Schirk2025] *Protected Fluxonium Control with Sub-harmonic Parametric Driving.*

J. Schirk, F. Wallner, L. Huang, **I. Tsitsilin**, N. Bruckmoser, L. Koch, D. Bunch, N. J. Glaser, G. B. P. Huber, M. Knudsen, G. Krylov, A. Marx, F. Pfeiffer, L. Richard, F. A. Roy, J. H. Romeiro, M. Singh, L. Södergren, E. Dionis, D. Sugny, M. Werninghaus, K. Liegener, C. M. F. Schneider, **S. Filipp**.

Phys. Rev. X Quantum 29, 030315 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1103/yx15-jyl7>

4.2 Category B – Any other form of published results

[Huang2025] *Theory of Multi-photon Processes for Applications in Quantum Control.*

L. Huang, J. Luneau, J. Schirk, F. Wallner, C.M.F. Schneider, **S. Filipp**, K. Liegener, P. Rabl.

arXiv:2509.16074 [quant-ph] (2025). <https://arxiv.org/abs/2509.16074>

[Wright2025] *Superconducting Qubit Gates Robust to Parameter Fluctuations.*

E. Wright, L. Van Damme N. J. Glaser, A. Devra, F. A. Roy, J. Enghardt, N. Bruckmoser, L. Koch, A. Marx, J. Schirk, C.M.F. Schneider, L. Södergren, F. Wallner, S. J. Glaser, M. Werninghaus, **S. Filipp**.

arXiv:2511.22580 [quant-ph] (2025). <https://arxiv.org/abs/2511.22580>

4.3 Patents (applied for and granted)

Optimization and calibration of quantum operations using sensitivity updates. M.

Werninghaus & N. Glaser. PCT/IB2024/062879 (applied).